

The level of motivation of athletic achievement among soccer players

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to determine the level of sports achievement motivation among football players under 19 years old, through a field study on the players of the Amal Chleghoum El Aid team for the under 19 category (case study), which won the championship for two consecutive seasons. The researcher used a descriptive approach and relied on Joe Willis' motivation scale as a tool to measure the level of achievement motivation. After collecting and statistically processing all data, the following results were reached:

- The level of sports achievement motivation is high among the players of the Amal Chleghoum El Aid team for the under 19 category.
- The level of achievement motivation among the players positively affected their athletic performance, leading them to achieve satisfactory results.
- On the other hand, achievement motivation is one of the essential psychological skills that should be present among football players.

I- Introduction:

Football in our era has become a phenomenon that touches the entire world and an endless passion; no sport has gained the fame and enthusiasm like football, which is loved by both young and old. Its championships have become some of the most important local and international sporting events, leading countries around the world to compete over the credit of the game's origin and spread. (Tariq Saad Habib, 2018, p. 7).

In recent years, sports training has been influenced by modern science and technology across various known sports. The training process has taken on an organized shape and structure that aligns with the new developmental state of the methods and tools used in training. Scientific and technological advancements have added many new and modern methodologies that fit the nature of the practiced sport and the age group of the trainees by selecting coaches who utilize the latest methods and approaches suited to specialized sports activities.

The topic of sports achievement motivation has become prominently important in the fields of study and research, whether in the psychology of competition or sports psychology. This topic particularly focuses on the factors that contribute to the initiation and continuation of sports practice, which in turn affect perseverance, ongoing training, competition, and the achievement of accomplishments. Motivation generally refers to the states or internal forces that stimulate and direct an individual toward achieving a specific goal. This interpretation of motivation has garnered significant interest from many scholars and researchers in psychology in general, and sports psychology in particular. This interest is manifested in the diversity of theories that aim to explain motivation. Among these theories that have the support of several thinkers in the field of sports, psychology is McClelland and Atkinson's Achievement Motivation Theory. Achievement motivation is defined as the athlete's readiness to confront the situations of sports competition and strive for excellence and superiority according to specific standards. This is achieved by demonstrating a high level of activity, effectiveness, and perseverance, reflecting the desire to fight and struggle for victory and to achieve the desired goals in competition. (Buthaina Mohammed Fadl Al-Wali, 2016, p. 132).

Through what has been presented, the problem of our study is represented in the following general question and specific questions:

- What is the level of achievement motivation among football players?

1-1- Partial Questions:

- What is the level of success achievement motivation among football players?

- What is the level of failure avoidance motivation among football players?

- Research Terminology:

- **Achievement motivation in sports:** A continuous interest in reaching a state of goal attainment stemming from a natural incentive, which energizes, directs, and selects behavior (Abu Al-Azaim Jamal, 1988). It is defined by Muhammad Jasem Al-Abadi (1998) as the amount of desire and inclination to exert effort in performing academic duties and tasks well.

- **Success achievement motive:** Refers to the effort made by the athlete to succeed in completing the duties and tasks assigned to them.

- **Failure avoidance motive:** A psychological formation related to the fear of failure, which is manifested in the cognitive concern about the consequences or results of failure, contributing to the attempt to avoid achievement situations and play characterized by a motive of distinguishing failure. Typically, one attributes their failure to other factors such as luck... (Mohammed Hassan Alawai, 1998, p. 259)

- **Football players:** A football player is an athlete who plays one of the various types of football. The main types of football are soccer, American football, Canadian football, Australian football, Gaelic football, rugby league, and rugby union.

Football is a team sport played between two teams, each consisting of 11 players excluding substitutes, with a round ball. There are 250 million players playing football in over 200 countries around the world, making it the most popular and widespread sport in the world. Football is played on a rectangular field with goals on either side and a grassy surface.

- **National Championship:** The league was established in 1962 when Algeria gained its independence. Until 1950, the competition was only held in regional leagues (Algiers, Constantine, and Oran). Some "national" playoff matches were held for the first time in 1904 in the first decade of the

20th century. Between 1920 and 1956, the winners of the North African Championship played alongside the winners of the championship from Morocco and Tunisia. On August 21, 2010, the Algerian Football Federation announced a name change for the league to the Algerian Professional League 1 to reflect the nature of the participating professional teams.

6-Previous Studies:

The first study: A study by Alal Sharif Hussein titled "The Effectiveness of a Proposed Training Program to Improve Skill Performance and Its Impact on Achievement Motivation in Young Football Players" at the University of Algiers 3 in 2015. This study aimed to determine the impact of skill performance on achievement motivation. The significance of the study was to highlight the role of psychological foundations in sports training and to show the extent to which skill performance affects the psychological aspect of football players, as well as to emphasize the importance of achievement motivation among football players and its relationship to the skill aspect. The study aimed to identify the impact of skill performance and its improvement on the motivation for achievement and the avoidance of failure. The research sample consisted of 25 players from the CFOR team in Ouled Fayet. The results of this study indicated that the proposed training program for skill performance development was effective in its positive impact, as it enhanced the quality of performance. It also had a positive effect on increasing the levels of motivation for athletic achievement in both aspects (achievement motivation for success and achievement motivation to avoid failure).

The second study: The study by Kamal Hamani was titled "Emotional Traits and Their Relationship with Achievement Motivation Patterns and Athletic Attribution among Football Players" at the University of Algiers 3 in 2015. The purpose of this study was to identify the distinctive emotional traits of youth football players and to understand the achievement motivation patterns characteristic of these players. The importance of this study lies in identifying the emotional traits, achievement motivation patterns, and athletic attribution, as well as determining the relationship between them. The study aimed to identify the differences in both emotional traits and achievement motivation patterns according to the variable of years of practice among youth football players at the level of Bejaia Province. The research sample consisted of 200 youth football players selected randomly from the research population.

The researcher reached the following conclusions:

- There is a correlation between emotions and sports achievement motivation, where emotions can drive achievement.
- A player's focus on outcomes and performance towards factors that can be controlled increases the effort to improve performance and results, as well as the motivation for achievement.

The third study : is a study from Muhammad Al-Amin University titled "Psychological Hardiness and its Relationship with Achievement Motivation among Senior Football Players Active in the Algerian Professional League 1," conducted at the University of Algiers 3 in 2023. The study focused on understanding the relationship between psychological hardiness and achievement motivation. The importance of the study lies in recognizing the nature of the relationship between psychological hardiness and achievement motivation among senior football players. Psychological hardiness is considered a modern topic that has attracted the interest of researchers in the field of sports psychology; it is viewed as a personal trait that helps players endure and adapt to various pressures they encounter during the sports season, whether in training or competitions. The aim of this research was to highlight the nature of the relationship between commitment and achievement motivation among football players, as well as to clarify the nature of the relationship between control and achievement motivation among football players, and the relationship between challenge and achievement motivation. The research sample consisted of 208 active players in the Algerian Professional League 1 of football.

II - Methodology:

1-Exploratory Study:

The exploratory study is the first step in establishing the foundations of research, aiming to familiarize with the study area and ensure its suitability for research. It also seeks to understand some aspects and concepts related to the research topic, in addition to:

- Ensuring the validity of the study tools and their appropriateness for the study sample.
- Addressing previous studies that have dealt with the same topic under investigation, reviewing books on sports psychology and sports science, as well as articles and publications related to the proposed study topic.

- Attempting to understand how to apply the research tool, which was represented in the motivation scale.

2-Field Study:

2-1-Study Method: The descriptive method was used due to its suitability for the nature of our study.

2-2- Study Population and Sample:

2-2-1-Study Community: The study community consists of football players under the age of 19 who are active in the Constantine Football League.

2-2-2-Study Sample: The study sample comprised players from the Amal Chleghoum El Aid team under 19 years old, with 20 players chosen intentionally.

3-Research Domains:

3-1-Temporal Domain: The main study was conducted from April 20, 2024, to May 20, 2024.

3-2-Spatial Domain: The study was conducted on players from the Amal Chleghoum El Aid football team, youth category, at the 11 December 1960 demonstration stadium in the city of Chleghoum El Aid.

4-Defining the study variables:

4-1-Independent variable: Sports achievement motivation.

4-2-Dependent variable: Football players.

5-Study tools: The study tool consisted of the Achievement Motivation Scale by Joe Willis (1982), which includes three dimensions: ability motive, success achievement motive, and failure avoidance motive. This is in light of the "McClelland-Atkinson" model of the need for achievement, and the list contains 40 statements: 12 statements for the ability motive, 15 statements for the success achievement motive, and 13 statements for the failure avoidance motive. Dr. Mohamed Hassan Alawi Arabicized the list, and based on some preliminary applications in the Egyptian environment on samples of players, the focus was limited to the dimensions of success achievement motive and failure avoidance motive, and the count was only 20 statements, which we used in this study, which is considered a case study of the team "Amal Chalgoum El Aïd" for players under 19 years old, aiming to identify their level of achievement motivation.

6-Statistical methods used: After collecting the results, we emptied and processed them statistically using the SPSS package by applying the - Mean - Standard deviation - Frequencies - Percentages.

III- Results:

- **Presentation of the results of the first hypothesis:** which came as follows: **"The level of achievement motivation for success is high among football players."**

Table 01: shows the mean and standard deviation of the players' responses on the achievement motivation scale (success achievement motivation).

Phrases the motivation of achieve success	Scale	It applies to you to a very small extent.	It applies to you to a small extent.	It applies to you to a moderate degree.	It applies to you to a <u>great extent.</u>	It applies to you very much.	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Number of points	Rank
Phrase (2)	Frequency	1	4	5	5	5	3.45	1.234	69	3
	Percentages %	5	20	25	25	25				
Phrase (4)	Frequency	0	1	4	5	10	4.20	.951	84	2
	Percentages %	0	5	20	25	50				
Phrase (6)	Frequency	0	0	0	3	17	4.85	.366	97	1
	Percentages %	0	0	0	15	85				
Phrase (8)	Frequency	5	9	3	1	2	2.30	1.218	46	10
	Percentages %	25	45	15	5	10				
Phrase (10)	Frequency	6	5	3	1	5	2.70	1.593	54	6
	Percentages %	30	25	15	5	25				
Phrase (12)	Frequency	1	3	9	4	3	3.25	1.070	65	4
	Percentages %	5	15	45	20	15				
Phrase (14)	Frequency	3	6	7	2	2	2.70	1.174	54	7
	Percentages %	15	30	35	10	10				
Phrase (16)	Frequency	5	6	3	3	15	2.65	1.424	53	8
	Percentages %	25	30	15	15	15				
Phrase (18)	Frequency	3	11	0	2	4	3.20	1.240	53	9
	Percentages %	15	55	0	10	20				
Phrase (20)	Frequency	2	2	10	1	5	3.25	1.251	65	5
	Percentages %	10	10	50	5	25				

-Analysis of the results:

From Table (1), it is clear that 5 occurrences out of the total occurrences, which represents 25% of the players, strongly relate to the statement **"I find it difficult to try to sleep after losing a competition."** Additionally, 25% of the players relate to it to a large extent, and 25% relate to it to a moderate extent. Meanwhile, 20% of the players relate to the statement to a low extent, and 5% relate to it to a very low extent. Furthermore, 10 occurrences out of the total occurrences, which represents 50% of the players, strongly relate to the statement **"I am willing to train all year round without interruption to succeed in my sport"** to a very high degree, while 25% of the players

relate to it to a large extent, 20% relate to it to a moderate extent, and 5% relate to it to a low extent, with no players relating to it to a very low extent. As for the phrase **"winning in competition gives me a great sense of satisfaction,"** it applies very much to 85% of the players and applies to a large extent to 15%, while no player fits this phrase to a moderate, low, or very low extent. The phrase **"I often feel fear before participating in the competition directly"** applies very much to the players at a rate of 10%, to a large extent at 5%, to a moderate extent at 15%, and to a low extent at 45%, while 25% of the players fit the phrase to a very low extent. It was also shown that 25% of the players fit the phrase **"I fear losing in the competition"** to a very large extent, 5% to a large extent, and 15% to a moderate extent, while 25% of the players fit it to a low extent and 30% of them fit it to a very low extent. We also find the phrase **"sometimes when I lose in a competition it bothers me for several days"** applies very much to 15% of players, and 20% of players find it applies to them greatly, while 45% of players find the phrase applies to them moderately, and 15% of them find it applies to them slightly, whereas 5% of players find it applies to them very slightly. On the other hand, 10% of players find the phrase **"I feel anxious before a sports competition"** applies to them very much and greatly, while 35% of players find it applies to them moderately; 30% of players find it applies to them slightly, and 15% of them find it applies to them very slightly. Regarding the statement **"I do not find it difficult to sleep the night before my competition,"** we find that 15% of the players strongly agree, agree, or are neutral. Additionally, 30% of the players somewhat disagree, and 25% strongly disagree. As for the statement **"Before my competition, I do not worry about what might happen in the competition or its results,"** 20% of the players strongly agree, 10% agree, and 0% are neutral, while 55% somewhat disagree and 15% strongly disagree. Lastly, for the statement **"I prefer to take a break from training after the official competition,"** 25% of the players strongly agree, 5% agree, and 50% are neutral, while 10% somewhat disagree and 10% strongly disagree.

- Conclusion:

From this, we conclude that the motivation for achieving success is high among the players, with an average of (4.85) and a standard deviation of up to (1.593). This positively reflects on their good performance in competition and achieving the desired level, which may be due to their feeling of comfort during training, in addition to the positive experiences they undergo during victories. Through all this, we affirm the validity of the first hypothesis and its realization, which states: **"The level of achievement motivation is high among football players."**

- **Presentation of the results of the second hypothesis:** which states, **"The level of failure avoidance motivation is high among football players."**

Table (2): shows the mean and standard deviation of the players' responses on the achievement motivation scale (after avoiding failure).

Phrases motivation to avoid failure	Scale	It applies to you to a very small extent.	It applies to you to a small extent.	It applies to you to a moderate degree.	It applies to you to a great extent.	It applies to you very much.	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Number of points	Rank
Phrase (1)	Frequency	0	1	2	9	8	4.20	.834	84	4
	Percentages %	0	5	10	45	40				
Phrase (3)	Frequency	1	0	9	5	5	3.65	1.040	73	6
	Percentages %	5	0	45	25	25				
Phrase (5)	Frequency	3	5	5	5	2	2.90	1.252	58	7
	Percentages %	15	25	25	25	10				
Phrase (7)	Frequency	0	0	0	4	16	4.80	.410	96	1
	Percentages %	0	0	0	20	80				
Phrase (9)	Frequency	0	0	0	4	16	4.80	.410	96	2
	Percentages %	0	0	0	20	80				
Phrase (11)	Frequency	0	0	1	6	13	4.60	.598	89	3
	Percentages %	0	0	5	30	65				
Phrase (13)	Frequency	10	1	1	5	3	2.50	1.670	50	8
	Percentages %	50	5	5	25	15				
Phrase (15)	Frequency	7	7	2	3	1	2.20	1.240	44	9
	Percentages %	35	35	10	15	5				
Phrase (17)	Frequency	8	4	8	0	0	2.00	.918	40	10
	Percentages %	40	20	40	0	0				
Phrase (19)	Frequency	1	2	4	7	6	3.75	1.164	75	5
	Percentages %	5	10	20	35	30				

- Analysis of the results:

From Table (2), it is clear that 8 occurrences out of the total occurrences, which represents 40% of the players, strongly agree with the statement **"I like the player who trains for extra hours to improve his level."** Additionally, 45% of the players agree with it to a large extent, and 10% of

the players agree with it to a moderate extent. Meanwhile, 5% of the players agree with the statement to a low extent, and 0% of the players agree with it to a very low extent. Furthermore, 5 occurrences out of the total occurrences, which represents 25% of the players, strongly agree with the statement **"I enjoy taking on any task that some other players find difficult,"** and 25% of the players agree with it to a large extent. We find that 45% of the players agree with it to a moderate extent, 0% to a low extent, and 5% to a very low extent. As for the phrase **"When I make a mistake in performance during competition, I need some time to forget that mistake,"** 10% of the players apply to it very much, 25% apply to it significantly, and to a moderate extent and to a lesser extent, while 15% of the players apply to it very little. The phrase **"I have a very high desire to be successful in my sport"** applies very much to 80% of the players, 20% to a large extent, 0% to a moderate extent, 0% to a small extent, and 0% to a very small extent. It also shows us that 80% of the players apply to the phrase **"I try with all my effort to be the best player"** to a very high degree, 20% to a large extent, and 0% to moderate, small, and very small extents. Similarly, we find the phrase **"My goal is to be distinguished in my sport"** applies very strongly to 65% of the players and strongly to 30% of the players, while 5% of the players apply to the phrase at a moderate level, 0% of the players apply to it at a low and very low level. The phrase **"Excellence in sport is not one of my core goals"** applies very strongly to 15% of the players and strongly to 25%, while 5% of the players apply to it at a moderate level and at a low level, while 50% of the players apply to the phrase at a very low level. As for the phrase **"When I make a mistake in performance, it burdens me throughout the competition,"** we find that 5% of the players apply to it very strongly, 15% strongly, 10% at a moderate level, 35% at a low level, and 35% of them at a very low level. The phrase **"luck leads to winning to a greater extent than effort"** applies very strongly to 0% of players, strongly to 0%, moderately to 40%, while 20% of players moderately apply to it and 40% apply to it very little. As for the last statement **"I can remain calm in the moments just before the competition,"** it applies very strongly to 30% of players and strongly to 35%, while 20% apply to it moderately, and 10% apply to it very little and 5% apply to it very rarely.

- Conclusion:

From this, we can conclude that the motivation to avoid failure is high among players, with an average of (4.80) and a standard deviation of up to (1.670). If a player encounters some form of failure and has some negative experiences, this leads to the emergence of a motivation to avoid failure in the future. This motivation is considered positive, as it contributes to increasing their level of motivation. This may be attributed to the players' interest in winning more than anything else. Therefore, the second hypothesis is confirmed, which stated: **"The level of motivation to avoid failure is high among football players."**

VI- Discussion:

From the above, it is clear that sports psychological preparation occupies an important space in the training process due to its effective role in preparing players psychologically to face various situations and emotions encountered during competition, positively reflecting on their performance and achieving set results. Its importance is no less than that of the physical, technical, and tactical aspects, as it is an integrated process.

Sports psychological preparation currently sits at the top of the training process pyramid; the higher the player's psychological and mental state, the higher their physical, technical, and tactical performance. Therefore, coaches should not overlook its significant impact on improving a player's performance level.

Achievement motivation is one of the essential psychological elements for football players, playing a pivotal role in many sports challenges in general and in football specifically. This is due to its great compatibility with the sports field, as every behavior has motivations or driving forces. Since motivation represents 70% to 90% of the training process, excelling in any sport requires the athlete to acquire mental, physical, and tactical skills. Here, motivation plays a role in encouraging the athlete to exert effort in learning these skills, persisting in practicing and mastering them, in addition to developing physical qualities. However, the sources of this motivation vary; it can be intrinsic or extrinsic, and its type and timing depend on its source. This confirms that the high level of achievement motivation among the football players of the Aml Chalgoum Eid team under 19 is one of the

reasons behind their athletic superiority and winning the championship for two consecutive seasons.

V- Conclusion:

After thoroughly conducting the research process under the title "the Level of motivation of athletic Achievement among soccer players" and after the researcher carried out a field study (case study) on the U19 team of Aml Chalgoum El Aid, we arrived at results that may add some scientific value to our research. In this study, we aimed to identify the level of achievement motivation in football players under the age of 19 who won the championship for two consecutive seasons and to highlight the importance of the psychological aspect due to its positive impact on players' performance and output.

The results indicated that the level of achievement motivation is high among the U19 football players of the Aml Chalgoum El Aid team, which won the regional championship for two consecutive seasons. This is evident from their readiness to train without interruption and their enjoyment of taking on any task, even if it seems difficult to some. They also have a very strong desire to succeed in their sports journey.

To ensure the best sporting results, coaches should focus on developing the psychological skills that players need, using all scientific methods to reach the required levels. Additionally, coaches should implement programs for psychological preparation, especially for this category, and strive to enhance the motivation for achievement among players due to its significant importance in reaching the highest sports levels.

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